

Mercuration of Compounds Containing a Reactive Methylene (-CH₂) Group by means of Mercuric Chloride. Part II.

By K. G. NAIK AND R. P. PATEL.

It is well known that when an aqueous solution of mercuric chloride is boiled with sodium bicarbonate, mercuric oxychlorides are precipitated (Mellor, "Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry," 1923, Vol. IV, p. 833; Millon, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1846, *iii*, 18, 372). These oxychlorides differ in their composition according to the experimental conditions and are usually expressed as double compounds of mercuric chloride and mercuric oxide. But it is possible to conceive that when to a boiling aqueous alcoholic solution of mercuric chloride and a reacting organic compound, a solution of sodium bicarbonate is added, the above double compounds of mercury, no sooner are they formed in an incipient condition than, would react with the organic compound present. With such a possibility, the organic compounds containing a reactive methylene group would, under the above conditions, give products containing the grouping >C:Hg. Such has actually been found to be the case.

The course of reaction may be expressed as :

The following substituted amides of malonic acid and acetoacetic acid when mercurated under the above conditions, gave products of the general formula :

(1) Malonmonophenylamide, (2) malonmono-*o*-toluidide, (3) malonmono-*p*-toluidide, (4) malonmono-*m*-toluidide, (5) malonmono-*a*-

naphthylamide, (6) malonmono- β -naphthylamide, (7) malonmono-1:3:4-xylylide, (8) malonamide, (9) ethyl malonate, (10) ethyl acetoacetate, (11) acetoacetanilide, (12) acetoacet-*o*-toluidide, and (13) acetoacet-*p*-toluidide.

That the compounds obtained do not contain admixed mercuric oxychlorides, is shown by the fact that they come out of the mixture as white precipitates which when separated and analysed were found to contain no chlorine; and at no time during the reaction was any change of colour observed. Furthermore, the mercury derivatives were insoluble in the ordinary solvents, whereas the original amides are quite soluble.

The resultant products decompose on treatment with dilute 0.25*N*-hydrochloric acid giving the original amide and mercuric chloride. With hydrogen sulphide they react quantitatively giving black mercuric sulphide. Potassium iodide decomposes the compounds forming the original amide and at the same time liberating two equivalents of alkali for each molecule of the product. Phenylhydrazine and hydrazine hydrate decompose the above compounds with the separation of metallic mercury. The above reactions clearly indicate the existence of a weak C-Hg linkage, which is usually found in compounds, containing mercury attached to a carbon atom in α -position to a carbonyl group.

From considerations such as, (a) the formation of a mercury derivative from ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl malonate, (b) the non-rupture of the C-Hg linkage under conditions which involve the rupture of N-Hg linkage (Ley and Kissel, *Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 1357), (c) the behaviour of the resultant compounds in a way similar to those having mercury attached to a carbon atom in α -position to a carbonyl group (Billman, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 2582; Schoeller and Schrauth, *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 2091; Petterson, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1912, *ii*, **86**, 498; Schrauth and Bauerschmidt, *Ber.*, 1914, **47**, 2740); (d) the quantitative decomposition by potassium iodide, and (e) the formation of dibromomalonamide, with bromine as advanced in a previous communication (Naik and Patel, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 185), the above constitution has been assigned to the compounds described herein.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Mercurimalonmonophenylamide, (I).— Malonmonophenylamide (1 g.) and mercuric chloride (1.15 g.) were dissolved in alcohol and

the solution heated to boiling in a flask. To the hot solution was added a solution of sodium bicarbonate (1 g.). The solution became turbid as the compound began to separate and there was effervescence due to the escape of carbon dioxide. The flask was then heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour to complete the reaction. The precipitate was then filtered hot at the pump, washed thoroughly with the alcohol and subsequently with distilled water. The product is insoluble in most of the ordinary organic solvents. It melts with decomposition at 275-78°. (Found: N, 7.25; Hg, 53.29. $C_9H_8O_2N_2Hg$ requires N, 7.44; Hg, 53.19 per cent.).

Action of dilute hydrochloric acid on (I).—The compound (I) on treatment with hot 0.25N-HCl went into solution which when concentrated and cooled deposited crystals of malonmonophenylamide, m.p. 164°.

Action of hydrogen sulphide on (I).—The compound (I) (0.6089 g.) was suspended in 30 p. c. alcohol and a slow current of hydrogen sulphide gas was passed into the solution till the precipitation of mercury as mercuric sulphide was complete. The precipitates were then filtered through a Gooch crucible and washed repeatedly with alcohol and water till free from hydrogen sulphide and the amide formed by the decomposition of the compound. It was then washed with carbon disulphide (20 c.c.) and pyridine (20 c.c.) to remove the sulphur which might have been precipitated together with mercuric sulphide. It was finally washed with alcohol and ether to remove the adhering carbon disulphide and pyridine, dried at 105-10° and weighed (0.3762 g.). (Found: Hg, 53.69. $C_9H_8O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 53.19 per cent.).

This indicates that the decomposition of the substance with hydrogen sulphide was quantitative.

Action of phenylhydrazine and hydrazine hydrate.—The compound (I) was decomposed when it was treated either with phenylhydrazine or with hydrazine hydrate with the separation of grey metallic mercury which settled down.

Action of bromine on mercurimalonamide.—The mercury derivative suspended in water was treated with an aqueous solution of bromine till no more bromine was absorbed. The flask was then heated to boiling and the solution concentrated. On cooling crystalline precipitates of the bromo-derivative and mercuric bromide were obtained. The precipitates were then filtered and washed with alcohol till free from mercuric bromide. The residue when

dried melted at 203.04°. It was identical with the dibromomalonamide obtained by the direct bromination of malonamide (Freund, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 782).

Mercurimalonmono-o-toluidide, (II).—This was prepared in exactly the same way as the corresponding malonmonophenylamide derivative (I). The product is insoluble in all the ordinary organic solvents and melts with decomposition at 257.59°. (Found: Hg, 51.6. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2Hg$ requires Hg, 51.3 per cent.).

Action of potassium iodide on (II).—The compound (II) (0.28 g.) suspended in distilled water was treated with an aqueous solution of potassium iodide (1 g.). Potassium hydroxide was gradually liberated. After a day, the liberated potassium hydroxide was titrated against 0.059N-HCl (23.3 c.c.). It was found that no more potassium hydroxide was liberated, even on further heating the mixture, showing that the reaction was complete in the cold.

The liberation of 1.915 equivalents of alkali indicates that the rupture of C—Hg linkage is almost quantitative in the cold.

Compounds similar to the above have been prepared by the interaction of the compounds (3) to (13) with mercuric chloride in presence of sodium bicarbonate under identical conditions. These have been tabulated in the annexed table.

Reaction products of mercuric chloride with substances containing the reactive methylene group.

(M = Mercurimalonmono—)

Name.	Formula.	M.P. (with decomp.)	Analysis.	
			Found.	Calc.
M-phenylamide	...	275-78°	Hg, 53.29 N, 7.25	53.19 p.c. 7.44
M- <i>o</i> -toluidide	...	257-53°	Hg, 51.6	51.3
M- <i>p</i> -toluidide	...	278-79°	Hg, 50.8	51.3
M- <i>m</i> -toluidide	...	265°	Hg, 50.9	51.3
M- <i>α</i> -naphthylamide	...	269°	Hg, 47.4	46.94
M- <i>β</i> -naphthylamide	...	270°	Hg, 47.3	46.94
M-(1:3:4)-xylylidide	...	270°	Hg, 49.2	49.5
Mercurimalonamide	...	286°	Hg, 66.62	66.66
Mercuriethyl malonate	...	Does not decompose till 300°	Hg, 55.01	55.85
Mercuriethyl acetacetate	...	Turns brownish black above 270°	Hg, 60.5	60.93
Mercuriacetacetanilide	...	205°	Hg, 53.66	53.38
Mercuriacetacet- <i>o</i> -toluidide	...	230°	Hg, 51.75	51.4
Mercuriacetacet- <i>p</i> -toluidide	...	243-47°	Hg, 51.3 N, 3.95	51.4 3.99

The authors take this opportunity to express their gratitude to the Government of His Highness the Maharaja Gaekwar of Baroda, for a grant which defrayed the expenses incurred in the work.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
THE COLLEGE, BARODA.

Received July 13, 1932.

